

Semiconductors in Europe: Innovation on the Move, Autonomy at Stake

Best practice category

Funding and Policy

Stakeholder group

Policymakers, The public

Value chain position

Policy and Funding

General Information

Sociedad Española para la Transformación Tecnológica (SETT) is a pioneering public business entity dedicated to financing and investing in advanced and transformative technologies linked to digital transformation, telecommunications, microelectronics, semiconductors, and other disruptive digital sectors. SETT plays a crucial role in reshaping Spain's strategic investment approach by fostering a proactive co-investment model that strengthens national technological capabilities, enhances economic competitiveness, and attracts high-value innovation projects.

SETT is recognised for its best practices in Funding and policy, skills development, and partner collaboration & open ecosystems. Through strategic investments, partnerships, and support initiatives, SETT aims to drive the growth of Spain's semiconductor and microelectronics sector, contributing to Europe's overall technological sovereignty and innovation leadership.

Activities and best practices

SETT stands out for its structured and multifaceted approach to fostering innovation and industry development. Some of its key focus areas include:

- SETT actively encourages the creation and consolidation of fabless companies through tax incentives and incubation programs. It also supports the generation and commercialisation of intellectual property in collaboration with research institutions and universities.
- By establishing strategic alliances with international manufacturers, SETT facilitates technology transfer and the development of production plants in strategic niches. Additionally, it develops prototyping and validation centers that enable industry players to carry out short-series production and proof-of-concept trials before scaling up.
- SETT creates public-private financing platforms that enhance investment opportunities for high-value semiconductor projects. It also implements financial support mechanisms through grants, soft loans, and investment funds, ensuring alignment with Proyecto Estratégico de Microelectrónica y Semiconductores (PERTE) Chip objectives.
- SETT launches specialised training programs, including master's degrees, vocational training, and technical courses, in partnership with universities and technology centers. To further strengthen the sector, it encourages national and international talent mobility through scholarships and exchange programs.

- To ensure a coordinated and inclusive approach, SETT has established a governing board that includes representatives from the public administration, industry, academia, and civil society. This governance model allows for a well-rounded and strategic vision for the sector's growth.
- SETT's initiatives help address several key challenges within the European semiconductor industry. By investing in local semiconductor capabilities, it strengthens Europe's position in a globally competitive market. Through targeted education and training programs, SETT contributes to the development of a highly skilled workforce. The organisation also fosters a collaborative ecosystem by bridging the gap between industry and academia, ensuring knowledge transfer and innovation adoption. By boosting IP development and production capacity, Spain moves toward greater self-reliance in semiconductor manufacturing, reducing foreign dependence.

Challenges addressed with this practice

SETT addresses key challenges such as low local production capacity, difficult access to structured finance, and the disconnect between academia and industry. By promoting targeted investments, national IP development, technology transfer and advanced training, SETT contributes to strengthening the competitiveness of the semiconductor sector in Spain and Europe, reducing vulnerabilities linked to dependence on external actors.